

THE EFFECT OF UNIT CELL SIZE ON IMPACT DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF 3-D BRAIDED GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Wei Li, Mohamed Hammad, Rona Reid and Aly El-Shiekh
(Mars Mission Research Center, College of Textiles,
North Carolina State University,
Raleigh, N.C. 27695-8301, U.S.A.)

ABSTRACT

Impact damage due to foreign objects is one of the critical flaws to affect the service life of a composite structure. 3-D braided composite material has much higher impact damage tolerance than laminated composites due to its fully integrated fibrous substrate. In this paper, the effect of the unit cell size of the substrate on the impact damage tolerance of 3-D braided Graphite/Epoxy composite material is experimentally assessed. The testing specimens are prepared using the 4-step (or Cartesian) 3-D braiding process with the 1x1x1 braiding pattern. Different unit cell sizes are achieved through using different size tows and different operating conditions. After the specimens being impacted under controlled impact energy, damages introduced are studied. Then a compression test is conducted to evaluate the compression strength of the specimens after impact. Results reveal that the unit cell size of the braided substrate plays a significant role in affecting the impact damage tolerance of the composite material.

INTRODUCTION

Three dimensional (3-D) braided composites are now used as engineering materials mainly for aerospace structures and show a prominent future for broader range of applications. A distinguished advantage of the 3-D braided composites is its fully integrated structure to resist delamination, so that the toughness of the material is greatly increased. As one of the most important properties of the composite materials, the impact damage tolerance of the 3-D braided composites has been assessed by several researchers [1-5]. During the course of these studies, no delamination was observed.

Besides the constituent fibers, the matrix material, and the consolidation conditions, the preform structure also plays a very important role in determining the properties of 3-D braided composites. Macro- and micro-structures of the 3-D braided preforms have been investigated by the present authors and shown that they are determined by the constituent fiber tows, the machine arrangement, and the operating conditions during braiding [6-8]. In this paper, as an initial effort to relate the microstructure to the properties of the 3-D braided composites, the effect of unit cell size on the impact damage tolerance of the 1x1x1 4-step 3-D braided Graphite/Epoxy composites is presented.

THE 4-STEP PROCESS

There are now mainly two groups of 3-D braiding techniques, namely the 2-step and 4-step processes. In the 4-step process, braiding is accomplished with at least four distinct motions in each machine cycle, while in the 2-step process, each machine cycle includes two distinct motions. Although both processes have the common advantage of the 3-D braiding technology, structures produced from them are not the same [9]. In the 4-step 3-D braiding process, the yarns or fiber tows are interlaced by cartesian braiding motions and compacted by a beating motion. The schematic drawing of a fully automated prototype machine built in our laboratory at NCSU is given in Fig.1. The machine has a movable beating mechanism driven by two motors. The braiding or cartesian motions are controlled by a microcomputer both in action sequence and speed. The shape of the braid cross-section is determined by the arrangement of the carriers on the machine bed. There are many different braiding patterns of the 4-step process, among which the most widely used one is the 1x1x1 pattern. Fig.2 shows the machine arrangements of a rectangular slab and an I-beam for 1x1x1 pattern. The carriers inside the marked frame in Fig.2 constitute the main-part of the arrangement. It is the shape of the main-part that determines the shape of the preform cross-section. A braid can be defined by the number of tows at each side of the main-part. When a main-part is fixed, the number of tows in the fabric and their braiding paths are also determined.

Fig.1 A Schematic Drawing of The 4-Step 3-D Braiding Machine at NCSU

Fig.2 Machine Arrangements of 4-Step Braiding
a) a rectangular slab; b) an I-beam

UNIT CELL SIZE

The unit cell is the smallest structural repeat and its size is an important quantity reflecting the structure of the braided composites. Fig.1 shows the real tow path and interlacing of the inside structure of a 1x1x1 4-step 3-D braid. The dotted lines in the figure outline a unit cell of the structure. Its volume can be calculated based on the cylinder shown in Fig.2 and, when the fiber tow has non-circular cross-section as usual, is given by

$$V=4d_1d_2h\sin\phi \quad \text{-----} \quad (1),$$

where V is the volume of the unit cell, d_1 and d_2 are the tow widths in the two directions as shown in Fig.1, h is the pitch length of the structure, and ϕ is the angle between the faces. If the cross-section of the tow is circular, then ϕ is approximately 90 degree and Eq.1 can be simplified as

$$V=4d^2h \quad \text{-----} \quad (2),$$

where d is the diameter of the tow. So it can be seen that the volume of the unit cell is proportional to both the tow cross-section area and the preform pitch length. The unit cell size can be controlled by choosing the size of the constituent tow and the pitch length of the braid which is determined by the braiding condition.

Fig.3 Inside structure of a 1x1x1 4-step 3-D braid

Fig.4 A unit cell

SPECIMEN PREPERATION

The experimental specimens were made using Celion G30 500 carbon fiber as reinforcement and Epon resin 828 with curing agent DTA as matrix. The size of the specimens is given in Fig.5 which is finally determined by the mould and the preforms were braided to approximately that size, so that no cut was conducted along the width and the thickness. As mentioned above, there are two factors that affect the unit cell size, namely the tow size and the pitch length. Two levels of each factor were chosen to make the preforms as given in Table 1. Therefore there are four combinations of the unit cell size. Two preforms for each unit cell size were fabricated. The braiding machine arrangements for each correspondent tow sizes are also given in Table 1. The braided graphite preforms were then impregnated with epoxy resin using vacuum impregnation technique. The fiber volume fraction of the specimens produced are in the range from 39% to 43%. Studies on the specimen cross-section indicate that the impregnation is quite uniform. Fig.6 shows a picture of the composite cross-section 3.7 μm under surface taken by the Scanning Acoustic Microscope (SAM) with 1.26 Hz wave.

Fig.5 specimen size

Fig.6 Specimen cross-section (X125)

Table1: specimen design

yarn size	machine arrangement	pitch length (mm)	
		7.62	10.16
12K	3x72	7.62	10.16
24K	2x48	22.86	22.86

Fig.7 the impactor

Table 2 Impact results

Specimen number	Yarn size	Pitch length	Unit cell volume	Fiber volume fraction (%)	Damage		
					area	length	width
1	12K	7.62	17.94	42.99	260.19	28.9	15.8
2	12K	22.86	53.83	38.97	453.35	109.1	14.0
3	24K	10.16	48.92	41.94	436.13	49.1	18.8
4	24K	22.86	110.07	39.77	799.03	152.4	14.9

unit: mm^n , $n=1, 2, 3$

IMPACT TEST

The consolidated specimens were impacted by a drop weight impactor built in our laboratory. The head of the impactor is a hemisphere with a diameter of 12.7 mm shown in Fig.7, and the falling weight is well guided to ensure the impact center. The specimens were impacted at a controlled energy of 27.6 N-m (20.16 ft-lb). After being impacted, it is observed that crackings are mostly following the directions of the fiber inclination, and fiber breakages are also present in the specimens. As an illustration, Fig.8 gives two pictures of the damage caused by impact. Fig.9 shows how the damaged area is affected by the two parameters, which is analyzed by a computer image analyzer. Increase of either the tow size or the pitch length yields an increase of damaged area. Fig.10 gives the combined effect of the unit cell size on the damaged area. The almost linear relation is most likely a coincidence and not to be claimed here. But as a general tendency the damage area increases as the unit cell size increases. Evidently the damaged area reflects the degree of damage caused by impact. More detailed results are listed in Table 2. These results indicate that the length and width of the damaged area are influenced more by the pitch length than by the tow size. This is because the large pitch length in this case yields much smaller tow orientation angles than those with the smaller pitch lengths. The cracks propagate most easily along the fiber orientation, so that it results in a long but narrow damage in the structure with small orientation angle, and vice versa.

(a) 12K tow, 7.62 mm pitch

(b) 24K tow, 22.86 mm pitch

Fig.8 Impact damages

Fig.9

Fig.10

COMPRESSION TEST

Residual compression strength after impact is one of the most important measures of impact resistance and damage tolerance of composites. The impact damaged specimens discussed above together with unimpacted ones were tested for compressive properties using a test fixture shown in Fig.11 on an Instron Testing Machine with 20,000 lb capacity at a cross head speed of 0.02 mm/sec. The resulting data are summarized in Table 3. The instrument was unable to break the two unimpacted specimens with large pitch length, which indicates that the strengths of these two specimens are greater than 280.34 MPa. This can be explained by the fact that large pitch lengths are in accordance with small orientation angles,[6,7] so that their strengths along their axial direction are supposed to be higher than that of the ones with large angles. The number 2 specimen, which has small size tow (12K) with large pitch length (22.86 mm) and is impacted, fails at the edge rather than at the damaged area, otherwise the strength could be higher.

Table 3 Resulting data of compression

Tow size	Pitch length	Strength (MPa)		
		unimpacted	impacted	difference
12K	small	265.68	201.86	63.82
	large	>280.34**	180.23*	>100.11
24K	small	228.23	193.55	34.68
	large	>280.34**	173.56	>106.78

Fig.11 Compression Test Fixture

* fail at edge, ** unable to break

Fig.12 Compressive strength (SP-small pitch, LP-large pitch)

Difference as in the strengths before and after impact reflects the damage tolerance of a material, explicitly smaller difference implies a better tolerance. From Table 3, it is seen clearly that for the same size of tows the larger the pitch length, the poorer the damage tolerance, which is in accordance with the result of the damaged area discussed above. But the effect of the tow size for the same pitch lengths is not quite clear due to some testing problems. From the result of the damaged area, it seems a higher damage tolerance should be associated with the smaller tow for the same pitch length, but the only set of data in Table 3 shows a reverse way. The compression strength of the unimpacted 24K, small pitch specimen is surprisingly small comparing to that of the other specimens, one possible reason is there might be some defect in the specimen; as a consequence of which, the small difference of the strengths before and after impact for this specimen is then also questionable. But there are still some other possibilities. One of those is when the tow size is very small as comparing to the specimen size, small variation of the tow size might not affect the damage tolerance significantly. If this is the case, relatively large tows could be used for big structures without sacrificing much damage tolerance. This can save a large amount of machine space. For example, the specimens using 24K tow prepared in this investigation occupy only about half the machine space required for those using 12K tow. Fig. 12 shows a plot of the strengths of the specimens versus the unit cell size and the two parameters. The rather arbitrarily matched curves suggest one possible tendency that the impact damage tolerance decreases as the unit cell size increases which is in accordance with what is suggested by the result of the damaged area. It is felt however that more investigations should be conducted to insure this trend.

SUMMARY

As an initial effort, the experimental investigation indicates that the unit cell size has a significant effect on the impact damage tolerance of the 1x1x1, 4-step 3-D braided Graphite/Epoxy composites. It is expected that this effect would be observed in other fiber/matrix systems. The unit cell size is determined by two structural parameters: the tow size and the pitch length. Contributions of these two factors may be different in different cases; a general tendency observed is that the shorter the pitch length, the higher the impact damage tolerance of the composites. Smaller tow size yields smaller damaged areas under the same impact energy, but the compression test did not give a clear picture about the strength difference. As a joint effect of these two parameters, it is suggested that the smaller the unit cell size the higher the damage tolerance in general. More detailed investigations are required to assess the effect quantitatively. This investigation should also include the compressive strengths of the specimens in the lateral direction.

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